

Hoton Al'adar Hausawa Cikin Roƙo: Tsokaci Daga Wasu Waƙoƙin Alhaji Musa Dankwairo

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Tsakure

Hausawa mutane ne da ba su aminta da zaman banza ba ko a ce zaman kashe wando ba, Bahaushe ya yarda da neman na kai, haka ya sa yake da wasu hanyoyi a al'adance da suke fara masa kwarin guiwa da nishadi a yayin da yake aiwatar da wasu ayyukansa ko bukukuwansa. Roƙo na ɗaya daga cikin sana'o'insa da mawaƙa ke aiwatarwa, inda suke amfani da kayan kida. Wannan maƙala mai suna Hoton Al'adar Bahaushe Cikin Roƙo: Tsokaci Daga wasu waƙoƙin Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun. Ta yi nazari ne tare fayyace gurabu daban daban da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun ya yi roƙo a cikin wasu waƙoƙinsa. Haka nan kuma ta kwankwance wasu daga cikin ire-iren hanyoyi da hikimomi da fasihin yake amfani da su wajen gudanar da roƙo a cikin waƙa. Maƙalar ta zaɓo wasu waƙoƙin maƙaɗin ne a kalla guda goma, waɗanda take ganin cewa a cikinsu ne maƙaɗin ya sarrafa wata hanya ya yi roƙo. Ire-iren hanyoyin da maƙalar ta lura maƙaɗin na amfani da su sun haɗa da: Ta nuna gado ko hali da sabo ko ƙoƙarin cin albarkacin wani domin ya roƙi wani abu ko wata alfarma ga wanda yake waƙe wa. Maƙalar ta bi waƙoƙin ne ɗaya bayan ɗaya, sannan ta fito da irin gurabun da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya yi roƙo kai tsaye ko kuma a kaikaice, sannan kuma ta fayyace hanyoyin da yake bi ya yi roƙon. A ƙarshe maƙalar ta gano cewa waƙoƙin Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun cike suke da gurabun roƙo. Haka kuma maƙaɗin na sarrafa hanyoyin daban daban domin ya Gudanar da roƙo a cikin waƙoƙinsa.

Gabatarwa

Mawaƙan baka na Hausa kan ba da gagarumar gudummawa baya ga nishadantarwa ko faɗakarwa ko ilmantarwa ko adana tarihi ko al'adu da sauran su ta fuskoki da dama. Mawaƙan baka na da hikima da azanci wajen isar da saƙo cikin armashi da annashuwa, ta haka sukan sako buƙatunsu ga waɗanda suke wa waƙa, wato su nemi kyautar wani abu kuma galibi akan yi masu kyautar abin nan da suka nema ko kuma wani abu maimakon wanda suka buƙata a cikin daɗin rai, komai kuwa girman roƙon ko matsayin abin da mawaƙan suke neman. Muƙalar ta yi ƙoƙarin bayyana gurbin roƙo da hanyoyin gudanar da shi da mawaƙa ke amfani da su amma ta ta'allaka ga waƙoƙin Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun inda ta yi bayanin yadda suke gudana a waƙoƙin nasa ko matsayin abin da mawaƙan suka nema. Waƙa sadarwa ce ta musamman na wani ɗan lokacin, (Bunza, 2016:10). Waƙar baka cike ta ke da hikimomi da azanci da nuna gwanintar harshe da mawaƙa ke yi, wadda ta nazarinta za a samu ilmi cunkushe a cikinta. Waƙa wata babbar masafa ce ta saƙar kalmomi ko mu kira ta "maƙera" ta ƙirar kalmomi. Kalmomin da mawaƙa ke lugude cikin waƙa su fitar da ma'ana a nan ne sirrin hikimar waƙa ke bayyana (Bunza, 2016:21). Nazarin waƙar baka wani fage ne da masana da manazarta da marubuta za su yi ta karakaina a kai domin faɗinsa . Wato dai ba a cewa nazarin waƙar baka ya tsaya a kan nazarin tarihin mawaƙi ko na waɗanda aka yi wa waƙar ko salon sarrafa harshen mawaƙin da irin azancinsa ko nazarin jigo ba (Alhassan,2016:1). Masana da manazarta da marubuta sun gudanar da bincike a kan waƙa, musamman ta baka da suka haɗa da Bichi, 1979, Yahya, 1984, 1997, 2001 da Funtuwa, 2000 da Dumfawa, 2003 da Dangambo, 2008 da kuma Gusau, 2003, 2009,2014, 2019. (Alhassan,2016:1). Nazari a kan waƙoƙin Dankwairo wani fage ne wanda aka jima da fara aiwatar da shi, musamman aƙalla, tun a shekarar 1973 da sashen koyar da Harsunan Nijeriya, Kwalejin Abdllahi Bayero Kano, Jami'ar Ahmadu Bello Zaria ya buɗe tattarowa da sharhi a kan waƙoƙin baka na Hausa (Gusau, 2019:Xiii). Duk da daɗewa da tarin bincike na masana da manazarta da ɗaliban ilmi da ma masu sha'awa suka yi a kan

wakoƙin Alhaji Musa Dankwairo, har wa yau ba a rasa wani gudummawa na ilmi da za a iya fito da shi ta nazarin wakoƙin na Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ba. kasancewarsa mashahurin mawaƙi da a ƙasar Hausa tarihi ba zai iya mantawa da shi ba. Ganin ba a samu wani aiki ko bincike na wasu masana da aka yi na mawaƙa akan roƙo ba watau a waƙar baka ba, wanda hakan ya haifar da samu gibi a bincike da aka gudanar a kan Alhaji Musa Dankwairo, domin a cike wannan gibi ne wannan makala ta himmantu ga bayanin gurbin roƙo da hanyoyin gudanar da shi, ta fayyace tare da ciro misalai na yadda suke gudana a waƙa. Hakan kuwa zai taimaka ƙwarai ga masu nazari wajen ƙara zurfafa tunaninsu tare da zaƙulo wasu batutuwan da suke zube cikin wakoƙinsa. A ƙarshe an kammala da naɗe wa a taƙaice. Ga bayanin su ɗaya bayan ɗaya.

Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun

Musa Dankwairo sanannan mawaƙi ne wanda ya rayu a ƙasar Zamfara ta arewacin Nijeriya a ƙarni na ashirin. Iyayensa Musa Dankwairo mawaƙan baka ne, saboda shi a wajensa Dankwairo ɗan gado ne ba hayen waƙa ya yi ba. Ana iya cewa bayan sanadiyyar Dankwairo a kan waƙa, sahararre ne a ta fuskar wakoƙin noma da sarauta da kuma masu-gari (jama'a). wanda ya yi tashe ga yin wakoƙin babbar sana'a ta noma da sarauta da sarakuna da kuma manyan mutane, to lashakka sunansa dole ya zama tamkar 'Tambari a ji ka sama'u'. Tarihin makada da mawaƙa na lokacinsa ba zai cika ba, ba tare da ambaton sunansa ba.

Al'ada

A iya cewa al'ada ita ke bayyana yanayin gudanar rayuwar al'umma kuma ita ce ke bambanta tsakanin al'ummomi mabambantan juna. Al'ada ita ce ke Fassara wace al'umma ce wannan ko kuma ta lura da hali wato nan ana maganar hali (wanda aka nuna). Dabi'a halin mutum ko al'adarsa (Alhassan, 2016:58). Al'ada na nufin dukkan hanyar rayuwar ɗan Adam tun daga haihuwarsa zuwa kabarinsa. A ko'ina mutum ya samu kansa duk wata ɗabi'a da ya tashi da ita tun farko rayuwa a wurin da ya rayu, ko yake rayuwa ita ce al'adarsa da za a yi masa hukuci a kai. Babu wata al'umma da za ta rayu a doron ƙasa face tana da al'adar da take bi, kuma da ita ake rarrabe ta da wadda ba ita ba (Bunza, 2006). A nan za a iya cewa al'ada kusan ita ce abu na farko da ke bayyana ko bambance tsakanin al'ummu, domin ko ga sutura ko abinci ko auratayya da sauransu, sukan bambanta a tsakanin al'ummu, domin kowa ce al'umma za a ga da yadda take gudanar da su. Wannan ya sa za a ga cewa yanayin shagulgulan bukukuwan Hausawa ya sha bamban da na wasu, haka mawaƙan baka na Hausa da ji ko yadda suke tsara wakoƙinsu za a fahimci cewa suna gudanarwa ne tare da bayyana wasu al'adu ko ɗabi'u ko tarihi da makamantansu. Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun ya bayyana wasu al'adu ko ɗabi'u a cikin roƙonsa. Za a ga hakan a cikin bayan da za a kawo a nan gaba.

Roƙo

Roƙo kalma ce mai nufin neman kyauta ko buƙatar wani abu a wurin wani. Roƙo na ɗaya daga cikin sana'o'in da Hausawa ke yi, da ake kiran masu aiwatar da wannan sana'a da suna maroƙa, wasunsu suna haɗawa waƙar su da kiɗa da amfani da kalmomin yabo da zuga da makamantansu. Roƙo na ɗaya daga cikin tubulan ginin waƙar baka. Roƙo na nufin neman wani abu ga wani ko a neman ma wani, wata alfarfar abu daga wani a madadinsa (Bargery, 1933:861). Haka kuma yana da ma'ana ta fuska biyu, watau Sana'ar maroƙa ta yi wa mutane kirari ko yabo don a yi masu kyauta, da kuma neman kyauta daga wani (CNHN, 2006: 374). Lura da bayanin ma'anonin kalmar roƙon ana iya cewa roƙo na nufin yadda mawaƙi ke amfani da wasu kalmomi na zuga ko kambamawa ko washi ko koda ko yabo ko nuna nasaba cikin hikima domin ya sami kyauta daga wanda yake ma mawaƙa. Makalar ta karkata akalarta ga fuskar ma'anar roƙo da nufin neman kyauta daga wani. Abin nufi shi ne an nazarci yadda Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ke neman kyauta daga wani a cikin wakoƙinsa. Duba da bayanin da suka

gabata cewa roko na nufin neman kyauta daga wani na wani abu mai amfani, abin kuwa ka iya kasancewa na cimaka ko sutura ko muhalli ko abin hawa ko kuma wata bukata ta musamman. Alal-misali neman kujerar Makka ko neman zuwa wata ziyarar bude ido. Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya yi amfani da hikimomi da fasaha wajen gudanar da roko ta yadda wanda aka roka zai fahimta kuma ya biya masa bukata gwargwadon hali. Gurabun rokon kuwa sun hada da; Roƙo kai tsaye, cin albarkacin wani, gado, hali ko sabo, da kuma roko a kaikaice.

Roko kai tsaye

A al'adance za a ga cewa duk da Bahaushe mutum mai gudun zuciya da koƙarin neman na kai, to amma a iya cewa an daga kafa wa mawaƙa kuwa za a ga mawaƙan kan fito fili su bayyana wata bukatarsa ga wanda yake wa waƙa kusan ma a iya cewa gwanancewa a harkar kan haifar da hakan. Wannan yana nufin yadda mawaƙi ke neman wata kyauta ta wani abu da yake da bukata daga wurin wanda yake wa waƙa, abun nan na iya kasancewa kuɗi ko sutura ko wani abu na amfani a cikin waƙarsa. Alhaji Musa Dankwairo yana amfani da wannan hanyar ta roko kai tsaye a wasu waƙoƙinsa, kamar dai yadda ya yi a waƙar shugaban ƙasa jikan Sule, wadda duk aka so ya kai, ta Alhaji Shehu Shagari, Tsohon Shugaban ƙasa, Turakin Sakkwato, da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun ya yi masa inda ya nemi ya ba shi kyautar mota tare da zaɓen irin nau'in motar da yake bukata wato mota ta shiga kirar 504 fijot (Peugeot) wacce take ɗaukar mutum huɗu, ya ƙara da kirar 'station wagon' mai ɗaukar mutum shida, sannan kuma da mota mai tamfal (pick -up) ta ɗaukar yaransa da kuma kaya, watau ya yi rokon ne domin ya samu sauƙin sufuri, kasancewarsa mawaƙi da duk inda wata bukatar tafiya ta taso masa zai tafi ba tare da wata matsala ba tare da walwala. Ga dai abin da ya ce:

Jagara: Sai ya ba ka mota 504,
: Sai ya ba ni mota 504,
: Station wagon,
'Y/Amshi: Duk in shige,
: Ina ta bugun turu,
Jagara: Kuma ka ba ni mai tanhwal,
'Y/Amshi: Ta ɗaukar kaya,
: Ta ɗau 'yan yarana,
: Shugaban ƙasa jikan Sule,
: Wadda duk aka so ya kai.

(Gusau, 2019: 319)

Maroƙa kan roki duk wani abu da suke ganin zai yi masu amfani ko suke da bukatarsa a wurin wanda suke yi wa waƙa kai tsaye ta hanyar ambato sunan abin, su nuna shi suke so. Kamar yadda Alhaji. Musa Dankwairo a waƙar ya yi arziki Mamma, hankalinka ya kwanta, Allah ya ƙara kyauta ma, ta Dr. Alhaji Mamman Shata, Dankwairo a ciki ya fito kai tsaye ya nemi a ba shi doki ko mota, sai yaransa suka nuna wa Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya nemi kujera (ta zuwa hajji ko sauke farali). Aikin Hajji na ɗaya daga cikin rukunin ko ginshikin addinin Musulunci wanda yake a matsayin wajibi ga dukkan wani mai bin addinin na Islama matuƙar yana da kuɗi da guzuri da lafiya watau matuƙar dai yana da iko, inda suke zuwa domin aiwatar da ibadar a ƙasar Saudiyya, galibi a garin Makka da Madina da wasu muhimman wurare da akan kai ziya. Wannan ya sa mawaƙin neman wannan kyauta ta kujera wadda ke nufin kujerar jirgin sama domin tafiya ƙasar Saudiya (ƙasa mai tsarki) don a sauke farali, inda aka ga mawaƙin ya nuna ta fi kyautar doki da mota waɗanda su ababai ne na jin daɗin duniya. Ga abin da ya faɗa:

Jagara: Doki za ka ba ni ko mota,
: Dankwairo roki kujera,

: Kowa ya samu duniya,
 : Sai alheri yai ta bidar gobe,*²
 ‘Y/Amshi :Ya yi arziki Mamman,
 : Hakalinka ya kwanta,
 : Allah kara kyauta ma,*²
 (Gusau,2019: 459)

Cin albarkar wani

Ga al’ada za a iya cewa Bahaushe mutum ne mai kara da riƙo da zumunci da girmamawa da soyayya tare da aminci, domin haka ake samun wani ya ci albarkacin wani wato ya samu wani alfarma ko ya samu wani abu a sabili da wani. Cin albarkar wani na nufin neman taimako ko kyauta ko wata alfarma a wurin wani ko wasu ta dalilin wani mutum da ake ganin yana da kima ko martaba ko matsayi a wurinsa. Galibi sukan zayyano abokai ko masoya ko wasu daga cikin ahalin wanda suke wa waƙa, da nufin a ba su kyautar wani abu domin albarkacin wannan da ake yi wa waƙar. Wannan hanyar roƙo ta cin albarkacin wani na ɗaya daga cikin hanyoyin gudanar da roƙa da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo kan yi amfani da ita ya yi roƙo. Za a ga misalin haka a waƙar Mai ban tsoro sadauki, Hassan ɗan Shehu Malam, ta Ciroman Katsina, Janar Hassan Usman inda ya bayyana cewa yana gayyatar Sarkin Gabas na Mashi tun da masoyinsa ya yi sarauta, harkar tasu ce domin haka komai ya roƙa zai samu, wato zai ci albarkacinsa ga sarkin Gabas na Mashi. A kan ce “so hana ganin laifi” masoyi kan sadaukar da wani abu nasa a hidimar masoyinsa cikin dadin rai, sanin haka ne ya sa Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya ambato masoyin Janar Hassan Katsina wato Sarkin Gabas na Mashi da nufin ya yi masa kyauta kasancewar masoyinsa Janar Hassan Katsina ya samu sarauta , domin haka ne yake cewa komai ya buƙata zai iya samu domin wannan taren nasu, wannan na ɗaya daga cikin nau’in hoton al’adar Bahaushe cikin roƙo. Ga abin da Dankwairo ya faɗa;

Jagora: Sarkin Gabas na Mashi,
 : Ina gayyarka murna,
 ‘Yan Amshi: Masoyinka ya yi sarauta ,
 : Harkar yau ku ad da ita,
 : Komai na so a ba ni,
 : Mai ban tsoro sadauki,
 : Hassan ɗan Shehu Malam,
 (Gusau, 2019: 183)

Har wa yau a dai cikin waƙar Mai ban tsoro sadauki, Hassan ɗan Shehu Malam, ta Ciroman Katsina, Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya gudanar da hanyar roƙo ta cin albarkacin wani inda ya bayyana cewa ya yi mafarki yana jin ƙarar injin ko mota za a ba shi? Yin haka ya daɗa tabbatar da cewa ana yin roƙo domin a ci albarkacin wani, domin kuwa an ba Alhaji Musa Dankwairo kyautar motar ta dalilin Janar Hassan Usman Ciroman Katsina. Ga abin da Alhaji Musa Dankwairon ya faɗa;

Jagora : Dankwairo na yi mafarki,
 ‘Yan Amshi : Ina jin ƙarar injin ,
 : Ko mota za a ba ni,*²
 : Albarkacin Ciroma ,
 : Kwairo an ba ka mota,
 : An kuma an ba ka mota,
 (Gusau, 2019: 184)

Kamar yadda aka gani adiyar waƙar sama an ga cewa duk da yake mawaƙin ya yi roƙo nea kaikaice ta nuna cewa ya yi mafarki inda ya ji ƙarar inji wanda a na fasarar da ya yi shi ne ko zai sami kyautar mota ne? sai ya daɗa nuna cewa ya sami kyautar motar albarkacin Ciroma. Duka waɗannan suna nuni ne ga ƙwarewar da mawaƙin ke

da shi wajen roko ta yadda wanda ake wa waƙar da masoyansa za su bashi kyauta cikin nishaɗi.

A wani lokaci Alhaji Musa Dankwairo idan ya yi rokon za ka ga wasu daga cikin abokai ko abokan mu'amular ko masoya ko ahalin wanda ya yi wa waƙar ke ba shi kyautar wannan abin da ya nema domin wannan da yake yi wa waƙar, kamar yadda za a gani a waƙar Shugaban ƙasa jikan Sule, wada duk aka so ya kai ta Alhaji Shehu Shagari, Tsohon Shugaban ƙasa Turakin Sakkwato, inda Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya nemi a ba shi motar hawa albarkacin girman mai girma wato Tsohon Shugaban ƙasa Alh. Shehu Shagari. Ga dai abin da Dankwairo ya faɗa:

Jagora : Na zo ka ba ni mota ta hawa,
 'Y/Amshi : Albakacin girman mai girma,
 : Shugaban ƙasa jikan Sule,
 : Wadda duk aka so ya kai,
 (Gusau, 2019: 316)

Gado

A tun azal Bahaushe mutum ne mai ruƙo da bugun gaba da asalinsa kuma ya yarda da cewa ana gado hali ko ɗabi'a da sauransu. Gado na nufin mutum ya mallaki wani abu a sakamakon rashin uba ko uwa ko iyaye su gaji 'ya'yansu ko matan aure su gaji mazajen su ko mazajensu su gaji matayensu da dai sauran su. Watau anan ana gado ne ta mallakar wani abu kamar kuɗi ko wata ƙadara. Ana kuma yin gado ta ɓangaren wani ya gaji wasu ko wani hali ko ɗabi'a daga wani cikin magabatansa. Shi kuwa Sa'adu (2020:108) ... mamaci dai ana gadon sa ta hanyoyi da yawa kamar auratayya ko ɗan haihuwa ko dangantaka, ko mace ko namiji. Mawaƙan baka na amfani da wannan hanya ta yin roko inda suke bayyana wanda suke yi wa waƙa da cewa ya gaji halin kyauta ko karamci ko wani hali na girma da sauransu. Alhaji Dankwairo yana amfani da wannan hanyar wajen roko ta gwadawa wanda yake yi wa waƙa cewa ya gaji yin kyauta, domin haka sai a yi masa kyauta kasancewar mutum na alfahari da bugun gaba da gadon gida ko kuma ya gaji wani hali mai kyau na gidansu. Kamar yadda za a gani a waƙar Mai martaba babu mai ja maka, Hassan ɗan Shehu Malam ta Janar Hassan Usman Katsina da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya ambato wasu daga wasu cikin ubanninsa wato Durbi da Sarkin Sullubawa tare da bayyana cewa a wurinsa kyauta gadonta ya yi, inda har ya bayyana wasu nau'ukan kyautar da ya gada waɗanda suka haɗa da; kyautar riguna da dawaki da kuɗi da ma wandon Kano, bisa haka za a iya cewa Dankwairo ya yi amfani da wannan hanyar nuna gado domin roko. Abin nufi nan shi ne wanda akewa waƙar da ya ji an zayyo halin magabansa zai ji ƙwarin guiwar bin hanyar da suka bi domin kar ya zama na baya ga dangi. Kamar yadda ya ke faɗa:

Jagora : Dan Durbi da Sarkin Sullubawa,
 : Ka gaji kyauta da riguna da dawaki,
 : Da kuɗi har da wandon Kano,
 : Mai martaba babu mai ja maka,
 : Hassan ɗan Shehu dodo kake,
 (Gusau, 2019: 187-188)

Za a iya ganin wani ƙarin misalin a waƙar Ci da ƙarfi Mamman Bello, Ya bi da arna, Ki sake mazan daga, ta Alhaji Mamman Bello Maitama da Dankwairo ya ke bayyana cewa ya gaji ƙoƙari wanda hakan ke nufin kyautatawa da karamci da makamantansu, waɗanda halaye ne kyawawan da Hausawa ke da su, inda za ka samu ga al'ada suna bugun gaba da kyawawan al'adar, tare da yin mu'amala mai kyau ga wanda ya marabce shi ko ya kusance shi. Ga abin da Dankwairo ke cewa:

Jagora : Ka gaji ƙoƙari,
 : Sa arna ladabi,
 'Y/Amshi : Ture haushi,
 Jagora : Dutsen fashin tama,

:Sa arna ladab,
(Gusau, 2019: 325)

Kamar yadda aka gani a bayanan da suka gabata, za a iya cewa Dankwairo na amfani da wannan hanya ce domin yin roko ga da wanda yake yi wa waƙan rokon, yayin da wanda ake wa ƙewar ya kan ji daɗi an bayyana shi da kyakkyawan asali na cewa kyauta ko karamci ko halin girma a wurinsa gado ya yi.

Hali/ Sabo

Hali na nufin wata ɗabi'ar da mutum ya saba aiwatarwa yau da gobe kuma abin nan ya zama masa jiki. Hali na nufin ɗabi'a, musamman ta mutum (CNHN, 2006: 191) Ɗabi'a suna ta tara, saboda Bahaushe ya karkasa ta zuwa kashi huɗu kamar haka: Akwai wadda Allah ya halicci ɗan Adam da ita, ana iya cewa kowa yana yin ta. Haka kuma akwai ta gado, wadda mutum kan gaje ta daga iyayensa ko zuri'arsa, musamman ɓangaren uwa. Akwai wata ɗabi'ar da ta saba wa waɗancan guda biyu, saboda koyon ta ko ɗaukar ta ake yi daga abokin zama ko abokin hulɗa. Bayan wannan tsari kuma, sai wadda kan samu dalilin sauyin yanayin rayuwa (Sa'adu, 2020: 111). Wannan maƙala idan aka ce 'Hali' ana magana ne a kan ɗabi'a ta mutum da ya saba da ita wato ta zama masa jiki, mawaƙi kan ambato tare da danganta wanda yake yi wa waƙa da ita, kana ya shigar da wata buƙatarsa ga wanda yake wa waƙar. Wannan ma wata hanya ce ta yin roko kamar yadda za a ga Alhaji Musa Dankwairo na amfani da ita, misali a waƙar Mai ban tsoro Sadauki, Hassan Ɗan Shehu Malam, ta Ciroman Katsina, Janar Hassan Usman Katsina ya bayyana cewa Janar Hassan ya saba raba masu kuɗi , saboda haka ya buƙaci ya kama wannan halin nasa na raba masu kyautar kuɗi wato Janar na raba masu naira. Ga yadda ya fada:

Jagora: Ka kama halinka da kas saba,*2

'Y/Amshi: Hassan yi ta ba mu naira,*2

(Gusau, 2019: 181)

A wani lokaci mawaƙa sukan zayyano wasu halayen wanda suke yi wa waƙar a aikace, inda suke nuna shi a matsayin mutum mai rabon suturu ko kuɗi ko abin hawa da makamantansu. Har wa yau za a ga ƙarin wani misalin a waƙar Mai Martaba babu mai ja maka, Hassan Ɗan Shehu Dodo kake, ta Janar Hassan Usman Katsina, Ciroman Katsina, wadda Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya bayyana cewa; Janar Hassan mutum ne mai kyautar mota, riguna, da dawaki, a nan ana iya cewa an yi amfani ne da wannan hanyar ta roko domin a samu kyauta, kasancewar mawuyacin abu ne mawaƙi ya zayyano wa wanda yake wa waƙa kyawawan ɗabi'a ko hali ya alaƙanta shi da su, a ce buƙatarsa ba ta biya ba. A taƙaice ga abin da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya fada:

Jagora: Janar Hassan mai rabon mota,

'Y/Amshi: Manjo Hassan mai rabon riguna,

Jagora: Manjo Hassan mai rabon riguna,

'Y/Amshi: Manjo Janar Hassan mai rabon riguna,

: Mai martaba babu mai ja maka,

: Hassan ɗan Shehu dodo kake.

(Gusau, 2019 : 187).

Roko a kaikaice

Wata hanya ce da mawaƙi kan bijiro da roƙonsa cikin waƙarsa a kaikaice ba tare da ya fito fili ya nuna buƙatarsa ba, wato yana yin hannunka-mai-sanda ne. Misali a waƙar Gagarau mai jiran daga, Ali na Magaji ci fansa, ta Alhaji Aliyu Dandoton Tsafe, da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya yi masa ya bayyana cewa matuƙar ana fitar da haƙi daidai to za ko a ji waƙa nau'i daban-daban, wato abin nufi da fidda haƙƙinku daidai a nan

Dankwairo yana nufin matuƙar ana yi masu kyauta ko karamci ko halin girma ko kyautatawa ko biya masu buƙatunsu, lallai kuwa za a ji shi da nau'ukan waƙa mabambanta, wato dai irin abin nan da masu hikima kan ce yaba kyauta tukuici. Ga dai abin da ya faɗa:

Jagora: In dai ana hid da haƙƙinku daidai,*2
 'Y/Amshi: Sai an ji launi iri bambam,
 (Gusau, 2019: 93).

A waƙar Dan'isa magajin Hashim, ya isa in gaisa, ta Alhaji Tijjani Hashim Dan'isan Kano wadda Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya yi masa ya gudanar da roko a kaikaice ta bayyana wasu falala da mawadaci ko wanda duk ya ciyar da dukiyarsa ko ya ba da dukiyarsa ga jama'a zai samu, domin kuwa mutane za su yaba ko gode masa, sannan tuntube daɗin gushi, ko ma a ce kololuwar falalar shi ne Allah da kan sa yana gode wa mai ciyar da abin hannunsa ga mabukata. Sannan kuma da akwai wata ribar kafa ga mai ciyarwa shi ne kamar yadda Dankwairo ya bayyana cewa Allah zai kara wadata shi, wannan hanya ce ta roko. A nan ana iya cewa faɗin fa'idar ciyarwa da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya yi ne don kar ya bayyana maitarsa a fili wato ta a ba shi kyautar wani abu ba kai tsaye sai ya buge da jawo hankalin ta nuna falalar da wanda ya ba da abin hannunsa ga jama'a zai samu. Ga abin da ya faɗa:

Jagora: Kowas samu yac ci yab ba mutane,
 : Sunka yi mai godiya,
 : Allah na gode mai sai ya,
 'Y/Amshi: Sai ya kara wadata ka,
 Jagora: Ahmadu,
 'Y/Amshi: Sai ya kara wadata ka,
 : Dan'isa magajin Hashim,
 : Ya isa in gai sai,
 (Gusau, 2019: 213).

Sakamakon Bincike

Muƙalar ta samu nasarar nazarin wata sana'ar waƙar baka, inda ta bayyana hoton al'adar Bahaushe cikin roko inda aka yi tsokaci daga wasu waƙoƙin baka na Hausa, an gano mawaƙan suna amfani da waɗannan hanyoyin wajen saƙo ko bayyana buƙatu ko neman kyauta, an samu nasarar bayyana hanyoyi biyar da mawaƙa ke bi domin yin roko da suka haɗa da; Roƙo kai tsaye da Cin albarkacin wani da Gado da Hali/Sabo da kuma Roƙo a kaikaice. Makalar ta taƙaita ga waƙoƙin Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun, inda aka yi bayanin yadda hanyoyi biyar da roko ke gudana a cikin wasu waƙoƙin nasa, hanyoyin kuwa kamar yadda aka faɗa ne a baya cewa yana amfani da su a cikin waƙoƙinsa, a wani lokacin ko ya yi amfani da duka ko ɗaya daga cikinsu kamar dai yadda aka yi bayani a baya, wato ko dai ya gudanar da rokon kai tsaye inda aka gano Dankwairo yana yin rokon ne gaba gaɗi ta yadda yake faɗin abin da yake so kai tsaye, ko ta cin albarkacin wani ita ma wannan hanyar rokon ma an ga yadda yake amfani da ita wajen yin roko ta yadda yake neman a ba shi wata kyauta albarkacin wani, ko ta gado wadda ita ma hanya ce da ake nuna wa wanda ake yi wa waƙar ya gaji kyauta, ko kuma hali /sabo an gano wannan hanya ce da mawaƙin kan ankarar da wanda yake yi wa waƙar cewa ai halinsa ne kyauta, sannan kuma a ƙarshe an ga yadda yake yin roko a kaikaice wato ba ya bayyana buƙatarsa kai tsaye, yakan sakaya, domin ba ya faɗin abin da yake da buƙata. Lallai kuwa an bayyana yadda Alhaji Musa Dankwairon Maradun ke gudanar da roko domin neman a ba shi wani abu, yakan yi roko ta gwada wa wanda yake yi wa waƙar cewa kyauta a wurinsa gado ne ko ya bayyana cewa wanda yake yi wa waƙar halinsa ne kyauta ko ya bayyana cewa ai

mutumin ya saba yin kyauta ko ya yi rokon kai tsaye ta neman a ba shi wani abu kai tsaye tare da ambaton sunan abin ko kuma ya yi rokon a kaikaice.

Kammalawa

Makalar ta bayyana yadda masu sana'ar waƙa ke tsirfar roko wato dubarar roko a cikin waƙoƙinsu, inda ta la'akari da yadda Alhaji Musa Dankwairo Maradun ya gudanar da roko a wasu waƙoƙinsa, inda ta kawo hanyoyin gudanar da rokon tare da cirato misalai daga wasu waƙoƙin da Alhaji Musa Dankwairo ya yi. Makalar ta bayyana cewa hanyoyin sun hada da; Roko kai tsaye, cin albarkacin wani, gado, hali/sabo, kuma da roko a kaikaice. An fayyace yadda suke gudana tare da misalai na yadda suke. An kammala da taƙaitawa tare da kawo manazarta.

Manazarta

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